

The deep SECRET to accelerated first-pass perfusion cardiac MRI

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Abstract

First-pass perfusion cardiac magnetic resonance (FPP-CMR) is becoming essential to detect blood flow anomalies. However, the need for real-time acquisitions limits the achievable spatial resolution and coverage of the heart. To keep both within a reasonable range, FPP-CMR needs to be accelerated. A Self-Supervised accelerated REconstruction (SECRET) DL framework is presented to speed-up reconstruction of FPP-CMR images from undersampled (k,t)-space data. The physical reconstruction models are used to train deep neural networks without requiring fully sampled images. SECRET achieves good quality reconstructions at a variety of acceleration rates, with significant speed-ups compared to the state-of-the-art.

Introduction

Coronary artery disease (CAD) is the occlusion of coronary arteries that causes abnormalities in blood flow to the heart. First-pass perfusion cardiac magnetic resonance (FPP-CMR) is rapidly evolving into an essential tool to detect blood flow anomalies¹⁻⁴. However, FPP-CMR time frames must be acquired in real-time to capture the passage of a contrast agent bolus through the heart, and hence, spatial resolution and coverage of the heart are compromised. Undersampled reconstruction methods have been proposed to accelerate FPP-CMR acquisitions in order to improve both resolution and coverage⁵⁻⁷. However, these methods can lead to long reconstruction times. This work aims to speed up reconstructions by obtaining the contrast-enhanced dynamic image series from undersampled FPP-CMR using a deep learning (DL) based reconstruction method. These images are then used to generate quantitative perfusion maps using a tracer kinetic model⁸⁻¹⁰. DL has already been applied to MR image reconstruction, specifically on knee¹¹⁻¹³, brain¹¹⁻¹⁴ and cardiac¹⁵⁻¹⁶ MR imaging, using both supervised^{11-12,14} and self-supervised learning^{13,17}. Occasionally, the network is unrolled to emulate compressed sensing (CS) iterative reconstruction, giving rise to a cascade of convolutional neural networks (CNNs)^{11-12,16}. Supervised learning techniques need fully sampled reference images to train the network, which are not available in FPP-CMR, particularly at high spatial resolutions. To overcome this limitation, a Self-Supervised accelerated REconstruction (SECRET) DL framework is proposed to reconstruct FPP-CMR images from undersampled (k,t)-space data.

Methods

Acquisition: Rest and stress FPP-CMR acquisitions were performed in 21 patients using a single-bolus injection of 0.05 mmol/kg Gadobutrol and a 1.5T scanner (Siemens MAGNETOM Aera). A free-breathing FLASH perfusion dual-sequence¹⁰ was used to acquire a low-resolution arterial input function image and three short-axis slices (basal, mid and apical) high-resolution myocardial images using the following parameters: FOV=340x308mm², in-plane resolution=2.2x2.2mm², slice thickness=10mm, TR/TE = 2.1/1ms, flip angle=8°, parallel imaging acceleration 3, saturation recovery time=100ms, total scan duration=60s. Undersampled datasets were generated for 3x, 6x and 10x acceleration factors using radial (k,t)-sampling.

Preprocessing: Images were resized to a spatial resolution of $2 \times 2 \text{mm}^2$, the k-space padded to obtain an image of 256×256 pixels, each slice was interpolated to a fixed number of (60) frames, and image intensity normalisation was applied. Image pre-registration was also carried out to correct for respiratory motion.

Reconstruction and Analysis: The proposed SECRET method combines physics, U-NET¹⁸ and residual learning¹⁷ to reconstruct contrast-enhanced dynamic images from the undersampled (k,t)-space data (Fig.1). Considering only the undersampled data when enforcing data consistency, the network can be trained using the physical models in the reconstruction¹⁷, without requiring fully sampled images. The loss is computed with the estimated undersampled (k,t)-space and the input, to guide the training phase.

Images were reconstructed for 5 patients using SECRET, CS and MoDL¹¹. MoDL uses supervised learning and an unrolled architecture for a number of iterations, K. Reconstructions were quantitatively evaluated against the fully-sampled images using normalized mean square error (NMSE), structural similarity (SSIM) index and peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR). Quantitative maps were generated using the Patlak model¹⁹.

Implementation: A 60-16-24 training-validation-test split was used. SECRET took ~ 30 min to train using the Adam optimizer²⁰ and learning rate of 10^{-4} . Training MoDL for K=1 took $\sim 1\text{h}30\text{min}$ and for K=10 $\sim 45\text{h}$.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the proposed SECRET method for FPP-CMR. Blue arrows represent steps that take place during training, and red arrows represent the steps followed when making an estimation. The CNN is based on the U-Net¹⁸. Skip connections are included to maintain information from previous layers, and to avoid the problem of vanishing gradients during backpropagation. At the end of the CNN, residual learning has been appended¹⁷, adding the average image of the zero-filled reconstructions.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the SECRET reconstructions from one representative patient together with the reference, CS and MoDL (K=1) reconstructions. Although SECRET reconstructions are slightly blurred, due to residual learning from the average image (also blurred due to residual motion), there is a quality improvement compared to MoDL (trained for a similar amount of time).

Figure 2. SECRET and MoDL ($K=1$) reconstructions obtained from 3x, 6x and 10x undersampled FPP-CMR data from one representative subject. Reference images are displayed for comparison. The right ventricle (RV), left ventricle (LV) and myocardial enhancement time frames are shown for one short axis slice. SECRET provides good quality images in a few seconds whereas CS takes about 1.5 min. SECRET requires shorter training times than MoDL and provides images that are visually better than those generated by MoDL.

Figure 3. PSNR, SSIM and NRMSE between the reference and reconstructions obtained with SECRET, MoDL and CS methods, for 3x, 6x and 10x acceleration factors, for all patients. While the performance of MoDL becomes noticeably worse as the acceleration rate increases, SECRET maintains good image quality even at high acceleration rates. CS and MoDL (K=10) show the best agreement with the reference, but reconstructions (and MoDL training) take longer than MoDL (K=1) and SECRET.

Quality metrics indicate that SECRET achieves a more consistent agreement with the reference as the acceleration factor increases than MoDL (Fig. 3). CS and MoDL (K=10) show the best agreement with the reference, but reconstructions take ~ 87.08 s and ~ 1.99 s, respectively, whereas MoDL (K=1) takes ~ 0.21 s and SECRET only 0.15s.

SECRET does not include any explicit regularisation term. However, due to residual learning, all reconstructions provided by the framework are inherently corrected. Such good PSNR, SSIM and NRMSE values obtained when the reference images are affected by residual respiratory motion, would certainly improve if regularisation were added.

Figure 4. Representative 1D profiles obtained from MoDL and SECRET reconstructions. The profiles correspond to the location of the line in the reference image. Note that although the images have been pre-registered, there is still some residual motion. However, SECRET reconstructions are inherently motion corrected due to the residual learning.

The SECRET quantitative maps are comparable to the reference maps, showing less blurring than MoDL maps (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Quantitative maps (KTrans) obtained from 6× and 10× undersampled data using MoDL and SECRET. The reference image is displayed for comparison.

Conclusion

A physics-informed self-supervised deep learning reconstruction framework for accelerating FPP-CMR scans has been described. SECRET provides good quality reconstructions at all acceleration rates, without using fully sampled data for training. Our method shows promising results, with the potential for improvement coupled with explicit regularization and parameter optimisation, which will be explored in future work.

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